

Robust and consistent weighting of observations in AGIS

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approved by:
reference: GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-083-01
issue: 1
revision: 0
date: 2010-08-20
status: Issued

Abstract

The proper weighting of observations in AGIS as well as the outlier treatment are reviewed. A new weighting scheme is proposed with a more physical basis than the earlier approach: instead of using a scaling by the unit weight error, the additional (excess) noise sources linked to specific sources and attitude intervals are estimated. The algorithms for identifying outliers and estimating the excess noise levels are described and tested by simplified numerical experiments. The algorithms are very robust and appear to function extremely well even with strongly contaminated observations. Several AGIS-type simple iterations are required for the weights and outliers to settle, before e.g. the Conjugate Gradients algorithm can be applied.

Document History

Issue	Revision	Date	Author	Comment
1	0	2010-08-22	LL	Incorporates comments by UL, including the new Sect. 4.1
D	1	2009-11-20	LL	Revised draft version
D	0	2009-02-18	LL	Created first draft

1 Introduction

In Lindegren (LL-077) the problem to be solved by the Astrometric Global Iterative Solution (AGIS) was formulated as the minimization of the overall chi-square goodness-of-fit

$$\chi^2(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{\ell} \left(\frac{R_{\ell}(\mathbf{x})}{u\sigma_{\ell}} \right)^2 w \left(\frac{R_{\ell}(\mathbf{x})}{u\sigma_{\ell}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the total set of parameters (source, attitude, calibration, global), $R_{\ell}(\mathbf{x})$ is the residual of observation ℓ as function of the parameters, σ_{ℓ} the (formal) standard error of the observation, $w(z)$ a downweighting function intended to take care of outliers (with $w(z) \simeq 1$ for $|z| < 3$, where $z = R/u\sigma$ is the normalized residual) and $u > 0$ is a scalar¹ intended to take into account unmodelled error sources not included in σ_{ℓ} ; ideally $u = 1$. In practice a different u is computed for each source.

The use of ‘fudge factors’ such as the downweighting function $w(z)$ and unit weight error u is problematic in any estimation problem, principally because they represent quite arbitrary ad-hoc corrections to the basic data model – in this case that the errors are gaussian with standard deviation σ_{ℓ} – without any specific physical justification.

In AGIS the determination of these factors is, for practical reasons, limited to the source update: only with the very small set of observation equations for a single source is it practical to perform the necessary iterative adjustment of u and R_{ℓ} (see Sect. 2.1). The intention was that the resulting u (per source) and w (per observation) could be used in the attitude, calibration and global updating (Lindegren, GAIA-LL-059). In practice it was however found that this can lead to instabilities, where successively longer stretches of data are excluded from the attitude determination (Sect. 2.2).

At the same time the use of a realistic model of the observation errors, and of how they are propagated into the final astrometric solution, is of very great importance for the final results. It is not enough that a good solution is found; it must also be assigned realistic errors in order to be astrophysically useful.

In the present note the whole problem of observation weighting and outlier treatment in AGIS is revisited with the aim to arrive at a more correct and consistent procedure.

¹For historical reasons, albeit somewhat illogical, u is called the ‘unit weight error’ of the data.

2 Current procedure and its shortcomings

2.1 Robust source update

We consider here the sub-problem to estimate the n -dimensional vector of source parameters \mathbf{x}_i for a single source i , based on $m > n$ observations with formal standard errors σ_ℓ . The current procedure is implicitly described by Lindegren (GAIA-LL-055), but for present purposes it is formulated here in a slightly different way. Including the empirical correction factor $u_i > 0$ (the unit weight error), the objective function to minimize becomes a function of both \mathbf{x}_i and u_i :

$$S(\mathbf{x}_i, u_i) = \sum_{\ell \in i} \left(\frac{R_\ell(\mathbf{x}_i)}{u_i \sigma_\ell} \right)^2 w \left(\frac{R_\ell(\mathbf{x}_i)}{u_i \sigma_\ell} \right). \quad (2)$$

Any sensible downweighting function $w(z)$ will be non-negative ($w(z) \geq 0$ for all z) and approximately unity for small z (in practice, $w(z) \simeq 1$ for $|z| \lesssim 3$). It follows from the first property that $S(\mathbf{x}_i, u_i) \geq 0$ and from the second that $S(\mathbf{x}_i, u_i) \rightarrow 0$ when $u_i \rightarrow \infty$. It is therefore not useful to make an unconstrained minimization of (2). Indeed, Lindegren (GAIA-LL-055) added the following constraint:

$$u_i = C \times \left(\frac{\sum_{\ell \in i} (R_\ell / \sigma_\ell)^2 w_\ell}{\left(\sum_{\ell \in i} w_\ell \right) - n} \right)^{1/2}, \quad (3)$$

where C is a constant $\simeq 1$ and $w_\ell = w(R_\ell / u_i \sigma_\ell)$, and n is the number of astrometric parameters (normally, $n = 5$). The expression in the denominator is a proxy for the number of degrees of freedom, and the numerical factor C compensates for the slight reduction of the RMS residual caused by the downweighting even when the normalized residuals are unit normal. For the particular downweighting function $w(z)$ proposed by Lindegren (GAIA-LL-055) (and denoted $d(z)$ in that reference), $C = 1.03125$.

Equation (3) is non-linear because u_i appears in the expressions for w_ℓ . Thus, the practical procedure adopted in the source update is to iterate the following two equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} & \text{minimize } S(\mathbf{x}_i, u_i^{(k)}) \text{ with respect to } \mathbf{x}_i \text{ for given } u_i^{(k)} \\ & u_i^{(k+1)} = u_i^{(k)} \times C \times \left(\frac{S_{\min}(u_i^{(k)})}{\left(\sum_{\ell \in i} w_\ell \right) - n} \right)^{1/2} \end{aligned} \right\} k = 0, 1, \dots \quad (4)$$

starting from some large value of $u_i^{(0)}$. Here, $S_{\min}(u_i)$ is the minimum value of $S(\mathbf{x}_i, u_i)$ for fixed u_i . This is how the unit weight error and downweighting factors are currently calculated in the ‘inner iteration’ of the source update.²

²It is not obvious that the constrained minimization problem (4) has a unique solution. This could depend on the adopted function $w(z)$. For example, it cannot be ruled out that the steeply decreasing downweighting function proposed in Lindegren (GAIA-LL-055) could lead to an instability in certain cases. However, we have not seen any example of this in the extensive simulation experiments.

Although the above algorithm seems to work quite well for the source update in isolation, even with a significant fraction of outliers, it is known that problems could arise when the algorithm becomes part of the AGIS iterative scheme. This is discussed in the next section.

2.2 Problem with the robust source update in AGIS

In the source update, a particular observation may have been singled out as an outlier just because the corresponding attitude estimate was not (yet) very good at that stage of the AGIS solution. In a future AGIS iteration, when the attitude had been improved, the observation would perhaps no longer look like an outlier to the source update. Downweighting such an observation in the source update is obviously a good thing, because it will make that process more robust. However, in the attitude update the downweighting of this observation is counter-productive, precisely because it carries information about how the attitude ought to have been corrected at the particular time of that observation. In fact, using the source update downweighting factors in the attitude update could easily result in an instability: A time interval with initially bad attitude data will have most of its observations downweighted, leading to an even worse attitude estimate in the interval, which will successively spread to neighbouring observations thanks to the smoothness of the attitude splines. This phenomenon has in fact been observed in some AGIS runs where the source downweighting factors were applied in the attitude update.

A simple remedy to this behaviour would seem to be not to use the downweighting factors in the attitude update. But this is not a good solution either, since some of the ‘outliers’ identified in the source update are indeed real outliers, which we do not want to include in the attitude (or calibration) update. And the attitude and calibration update processes involve too many observations per solution to implement an efficient independent outlier detection algorithm, since that would require an inner iteration loop over the observations.

In order to eliminate this potential instability while still using the power of the source update for identifying deviating observations, it is necessary to model the attitude-induced errors, in the current iteration, as functions of time. This leads to the modified error model described below.

3 A more realistic error model

The most important noise contributions to any observation ℓ are:

- Photon (and readout) noise, represented by the formal standard deviation σ_ℓ determined in the centroiding algorithm. In AGIS, this is a fixed and known number for every observation.
- Source noise, represented by the standard deviation ϵ_i which is a characteristic of the source i . The origin of this noise could be stellar duplicity, perturbing background

objects, or similar. For a primary source it should be negligible.

- Attitude errors, represented by the standard deviations ϵ_{AL} (along scan), ϵ_{ACP} (across scan in the preceding field) and ϵ_{ACF} (across scan in the following field). These are in general functions of time. They are initially large but decrease during the AGIS iterations. On convergence, they should have reached stable values representing the residual attitude modelling errors.
- Outliers, i.e. large deviations that cannot be explained by any of the above noise sources.

In addition there are calibration errors, which like the attitude errors decrease with successive AGIS iterations to reach a final plateau. However, their contribution to the total error of any observation is expected to be small, and is therefore neglected here, or considered part of the attitude errors.

For each observation ℓ the total noise can be considered as made up of two components, namely the photon noise σ_ℓ and the excess noise ϵ_ℓ , where

$$\epsilon_\ell^2 = \epsilon_i^2 + \epsilon_a^2(t_\ell). \quad (5)$$

Subscript a here stands for AL, ACP or ACF (whichever is relevant for the observation). While the photon noise is to a very good approximation white (i.e., uncorrelated between the observations), the excess errors have some important correlations. In particular they are expected to be nearly constant over a field transit (or more). These correlations have to be neglected for the purpose of the least-squares estimation: there is no practical way to take them into account.

With the new error model introduced in place of (1), the objective function to minimize becomes

$$\chi^2(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_\ell \frac{R_\ell(\mathbf{x})^2}{\sigma_\ell^2 + \epsilon_\ell^2} w\left(\frac{R_\ell(\mathbf{x})}{\sqrt{\sigma_\ell^2 + \epsilon_\ell^2}}\right). \quad (6)$$

The main differences with respect to the old formulation are: (i) that the excess noise is quadratically added to σ_ℓ , instead of being accounted for by the multiplicative factor u_i ; and (ii) the separation of the excess noise into a source-dependent and a time-dependent component in Eq. (5). As before, the outliers are taken care of by the downweighting function $w(z)$, but any stretch of bad attitude will now (eventually) have a correspondingly large ϵ_a which will prevent that the observations are downweighted and not used in any of the update blocks, notably attitude where they are crucially needed. From a physical viewpoint, the modification in (6) clearly makes sense. The question is if it can be made to work in the practical solution.

As in Sect. 2.1, it is necessary to constrain the extra noise components by some normalization procedure. The main problem is how to estimate ϵ_i for each source, jointly with $\epsilon_a(t)$ (for $a = AL, ACP, \text{ and } ACF$). In the following we outline a possible procedure.

3.1 Source update

We assume here that some initial estimate of $\epsilon_a(t)$ is available (it could be $= 0$). Improved estimates will later be obtained as discussed in Sect. 3.2. The estimation of ϵ_i and $\epsilon_a(t)$ then proceeds, alternately, as part of a sequence of simple AGIS iterations.

Since $\epsilon_a(t)$ is assumed to be known, let us for brevity introduce $\tilde{\sigma}_\ell^2 = \sigma_\ell^2 + \epsilon_a^2(t_\ell)$, so that the total variance becomes $\sigma_\ell^2 + \epsilon_\ell^2 = \tilde{\sigma}_\ell^2 + \epsilon_i^2$. We now seek to minimize

$$S(\mathbf{x}_i, \epsilon_i^2) = \sum_{\ell \in i} \frac{R_\ell^2(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\tilde{\sigma}_\ell^2 + \epsilon_i^2} w \left(\frac{R_\ell(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\sqrt{\tilde{\sigma}_\ell^2 + \epsilon_i^2}} \right) \quad (7)$$

subject to the constraint

$$S_{\min}(\epsilon_i^2) \leq \nu_i, \quad (8)$$

where ν_i is the number of degrees of freedom in the source update solution, i.e., the expected value of S if the noise variances are correctly estimated. If $S_{\min}(0) \leq \nu_i$, then $\epsilon_i = 0$ is adopted.

The degrees of freedom is here estimated as

$$\nu_i = \sum_{\ell \in i} 1 - m_{\text{out}} - n, \quad (9)$$

where $n = 5$ is the number of astrometric parameters and m_{out} the number of identified outliers. An observation ℓ is counted as an outlier if the downweighting factor w_ℓ in (7) is less than 0.2. This limit was found to give a good correspondence between the simulated and recovered number of outliers in numerous experiments, even using different downweighting functions.

A practical algorithm for solving the non-linear problem (7)–(8) is outlined in Appendix A.

The solution will return a positive value for the excess source error ϵ_i as soon as $S_{\min}(0) > \nu_i$. If this is much smaller than the average σ_ℓ for the source, it is probably not significant. However, the significance of any positive ϵ_i can more easily be judged from an auxiliary statistic that can be computed almost for free. Under the null hypothesis ($\epsilon_i = 0$ and the attitude errors are correctly estimated) $S_{\min}(0)$ has approximately the chi-square distribution with ν_i degrees of freedom. That is, the expected value is ν_i and the variance is $2\nu_i$. Thus, we may take

$$D = \frac{S_{\min}(0) - \nu_i}{\sqrt{2\nu_i}} \quad (10)$$

as a measure of the significance of the estimated ϵ_i , with $D > 2$ indicating a probably significant value.

The excess source error ϵ_i (after convergence of the AGIS iterations) is a suitable statistic for source relegation, since it directly indicates how much excess noise the source contributes to the attitude and calibration. As such, it is more relevant than the unit weight error (u_i).

3.2 Estimating the excess attitude noise

In parallel with the source updating, the residuals from the adjusted source solution are accumulated in such a way that they allow the excess attitude noise $\epsilon_a(t)$ (for $a = \text{AL, ACP, and ACF}$) to be estimated when all the sources have been processed. The algorithm is very simple.

Divide the time line t into buckets $[t_j, t_{j+1})$ such that each bucket (j) will contain a sufficient number of observations, also in the AC direction. The size (duration) of a bucket should be several knot intervals for the attitude spline, but the boundaries t_j need not in any other way be related to the knot sequence of the spline. There is one set of buckets for each attitude component (AL, ACP, ACF). Let $\ell \in ja$ signify that observation ℓ belongs to bucket j and attitude component a . After the source updating, the attitude noise in bucket j is estimated as

$$\epsilon_a^2(t_j \leq t < t_{j+1}) = \max \left(0, Q_{0.68} \left(R_\ell^2 - \sigma_\ell^2 - \epsilon_i^2 \right) \right), \quad (11)$$

where $Q_{0.68}()$ is the 68% quantile of the argument values. It is important to note that the downweighting factors w_ℓ determined during the source updating is not used here to eliminate possible outliers; this function is instead taken care of by using the quantile to compute the typical excess variance in the attitude bucket. This means that if the ‘outliers’ detected by the source update were actually caused by a stretch of bad attitude, then this will be recognized by a large value of the 68% quantile in (11).

In the subsequent attitude update, the downweighting factor w_ℓ is re-computed based on the residual from the previous source update but with a value for the total variance, $\sigma_\ell^2 + \sigma_i^2 + \epsilon_a^2$, using the newly updated ϵ_a^2 . Thus, in the subsequent attitude update, only the ‘true’ outliers – that are not due to the bad attitude – will be downweighted (cf. Sect. 4.1)

The functions $\epsilon_a(t)$ are obviously an extremely useful diagnostic for the progress of the AGIS iterations as well as (after convergence) for the quality of the attitude modelling and/or data. They can be plotted as a function of time, and the quantity of data is such that human inspection is feasible, if needed. They are also needed for setting the detection threshold for micrometeoroid impacts.

One remaining problem is how to compute the quantile in (11) in an efficient way, without having to store billions of residuals. For the small-scale numerical experiments described in Sect. 5.2 it was no problem to store the residuals, and therefore an exact algorithm (in MATLAB) was used; however, for the implementation in AGIS and AGISLab a more economical, albeit approximate, solution is needed. This problem is discussed in Appendix B.

4 Iterations

4.1 Use of the excess noises in successive iterations

In the simple iteration scheme of AGIS, the source, attitude and calibration update are executed in sequence, once per iteration. The above estimation of downweighting factors and the excess noise components ϵ_i and $\epsilon_a(t)$ must be done in parallel with the cyclical updating of the source, attitude and calibration parameters. Exactly which values of the excess noises are used in each update process partly depends on their order and whether some of them are done in parallel. The following considerations apply to AGIS as currently implemented.

Let us say we are in iteration k . We start with a source update and then do the attitude, calibration, and global updates in parallel. The pattern of using and calculating new noise values (and thus weights) in iteration k is then:

Process	Using	Calculating
Source update	$\epsilon_a^{(k-1)}$ and $\epsilon_i^{(k)}$	$\epsilon_i^{(k)}$
Attitude update	$\epsilon_a^{(k-1)}$ and $\epsilon_i^{(k)}$	$\epsilon_a^{(k)}$
Calibration update	$\epsilon_a^{(k-1)}$ and $\epsilon_i^{(k)}$	(nothing)
Global update	$\epsilon_a^{(k-1)}$ and $\epsilon_i^{(k)}$	(nothing)

In the source update we are using the excess attitude noise from the previous iteration $k - 1$ and the most-recent excess source noise (which we are calculating as part of the source update itself). In the attitude update we are calculating the new excess attitude noise for iteration k . At the same time we are calculating updates which, however, has to use the excess noise from iteration $k - 1$ as $\epsilon_a^{(k)}$ is not yet available (otherwise we would need two passes through the data). In the calibration and global updates we use the weights as in the source and attitude updates but calculate no new noise values.

4.2 Use in the Conjugate Gradients scheme

Recomputing the excess noises and downweighting factors in each iteration means that the weights of the observations are changing all the time, even from the source update to the subsequent attitude update. These processes therefore solve parts of a slightly *different* least-squares problem each time. This works fine with the simple iteration scheme, but would not work with the Conjugate Gradients scheme, which must operate on a fixed set of observations and weights.

Consequently, the following iteration scheme is proposed:

1. For the first X AGIS iterations, use the simple iteration scheme (with or without acceleration) with the currently described weight adjustment methods enabled.
2. Thereafter, fix the downweighting factors and excess noise estimates to the values obtained in the last simple iteration, and start the Conjugate Gradient scheme.
3. After convergence of the Conjugate Gradients, one could optionally make additional iterations with the weight adjustment enabled.
4. The Conjugate Gradients scheme is then again used to obtain the final solution.

Obviously, the last two steps could be repeated as many times as necessary. Possibly, they could replace the ‘restarting’ of the Conjugate Gradients scheme that is sometimes necessary due to the accumulation of rounding errors.

5 Numerical experiments

The algorithms outlined above and in Appendix A have been tested by numerical simulations representing simplified problems, but preserving the main features from AGIS. All simulations were made in MATLAB, and the source code is available in the SVN repository for this TN.

5.1 Testing the source update algorithm

The source update algorithm described in Appendix A was tested in the following way. First, the design matrix \mathbf{A} for the AL observations in the AF was generated for 10 random locations on the sky, assuming a 5 yr mission, the nominal scanning law, and nominal focal plane layout. Then, for each \mathbf{A} , 100 different examples of the ‘true’ astrometric parameters \mathbf{x} were generated using normal random deviates with a standard deviation of 1000 units in each astrometric parameter. Thus, a total of 1000 examples were generated. For each example, the right-hand side was calculated as

$$\mathbf{h} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}_1 + \mathbf{e}_2 \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{e}_1 is the photon and attitude noise (standard deviation $\tilde{\sigma}$) and \mathbf{e}_2 the excess source noise (standard deviation ϵ). The individual standard deviations $\tilde{\sigma}_\ell$ were drawn from a log-normal distribution with mean value 100 units and a dispersion of 0.5 neper. For the excess source noise, the same value e_2 was used for all nine observations in a field-of-view transit.

Outliers were simulated in the following way. Let $0 \leq p < 1$ be the requested fraction of outliers, and $f \geq 1$ some given multiplicative factor. For each observation, the total error $e_1 + e_2$ is then multiplied by a factor f with probability p . Putting $p = 0$ (or $f = 1$) gives no outliers. A large value of f (say $f = 10^6$) produces what we may call ‘hard’ outliers; that is, they are (usually) very conspicuous and therefore relatively easy to filter out. A relatively

small value (say $f = 10$) produces ‘soft’ outliers that are more difficult to filter out cleanly, but may be more representative of real outliers in the Gaia observations. In order to study the behaviour of the source update algorithm for a wide variety of outlier characteristics, p was for each example taken to be a random number between 0 and 0.6, generated as $p = 0.6u^2$, where u is a uniform variate in $[0, 1]$. Taking the square of u increases the fraction of small f .

For a given combination of ϵ and f , the 1000 examples thus generated were put through procedure \mathcal{P} (Appendix A). the results are graphically presented in two different plots. The first plot (Figs. 1 and 2) shows the estimated number of outliers, m_{out} , against the actual number of outliers, i.e., the number of times the factor f was applied when generating the noise. It should be noted that the application of f (especially when f is not very large) does not necessarily produce a real outlier, namely, if $e_1 + e_2$ already happens to be small. Thus, we should in general expect m_{out} to be slightly smaller than the nominal generated number (especially for small f). Figure 1 shows the results for $f = 100$ (i.e., moderately ‘hard’ outliers) with different levels of ϵ . In all cases the outlier detection works very well up to a outlier fraction of 25–30%, after which it breaks down. Figure 2 shows the results for ‘soft’ outlier ($f = 10$). In this case the outlier detection breaks down somewhat earlier, perhaps at around 10%. Also, not all outliers are caught, which is to be expected in the soft case as explained above.

The second kind of plot gives the estimated excess source noise ϵ as a function of the actual number of outliers. This is shown in Fig. 3 for the ‘hard’ outliers ($f = 100$) and in Fig. 4 for the ‘soft’ ($f = 10$). Open circles denote estimates of ϵ that are considered insignificant ($D < 2$).

FIGURE 1: Fraction of detected outliers plotted against the actual fraction of outliers, in experiments with different levels of the excess source noise (ϵ). The outliers in this case are moderately ‘hard’, using $f = 100$. Note: due to the use of logarithmic scales, what is actually plotted is the fraction $(m_{\text{out}} + 1)/m$. The average m is 867.

FIGURE 2: Fraction of detected outliers plotted against the actual fraction of outliers, in experiments with different levels of the excess source noise (ϵ). The outliers in this case are rather ‘soft’, using $f = 10$. Note: due to the use of logarithmic scales, what is actually plotted is the fraction $(m_{\text{out}} + 1)/m$. The average m is 867.

FIGURE 3: Estimated excess source noise (ϵ) plotted against the actual fraction of outliers, in experiments with different actual levels of ϵ . The outliers in this case are moderately ‘hard’, using $f = 100$. Circles indicate insignificant values ($D < 2$). Note: due to the use of logarithmic scales, what is actually plotted is $(m_{\text{out}} + 1)/m$ for the fraction of outliers, and $1 + \epsilon$ on the vertical scale.

FIGURE 4: Estimated excess source noise (ϵ) plotted against the actual fraction of outliers, in experiments with different actual levels of ϵ . The outliers in this case are ‘soft’, using $f = 10$. Circles indicate insignificant values ($D < 2$). Note: due to the use of logarithmic scales, what is actually plotted is $(m_{\text{out}} + 1)/m$ for the fraction of outliers, and $1 + \epsilon$ on the vertical scale.

5.2 Testing the source/attitude iteration algorithm

In order to demonstrate that it is actually possible to separate the source-related and attitude-related excess noises, even in the presence of outliers, experiments were carried out that simulate successive AGIS iterations using (7)–(8) and (11) in conjunction with the source and attitude updates.

The AL observations of 100 stars ($i = 1$ through 100, each with five astrometric parameters) were simulated, and each field-of-view transit (consisting of nine consecutive observations) was assigned to an attitude ‘bucket’. Only 200 such buckets were used ($j = 1$ through 200), and the field transits were randomly assigned to these without regard to the actual observation times. This artifice was used in order to get a ‘closed’ system of source and attitude parameters with a very small total number of unknowns. The standard error of each observation (σ_ℓ) was set to a log-normally distributed number with mean value 100 units and a dispersion of 0.5 neper. The initial offset of the astrometric parameters of each source, as well as the true attitude of the each bucket, were taken from a random normal distribution with zero mean and a standard deviation of 1000 units. The *true* right-hand side of the observation equations immediately follows from the design matrix and true astrometric parameters of each source, and the true attitude offset of the buckets. To these values, a random noise was added, independently for each observation, with variance equal to $\sigma_\ell^2 + \epsilon_i^2 + \epsilon_{aj}^2$. In addition, outliers were simulated by amplifying the noise by a certain factor (f) for a certain fraction of the observations, exactly as in Sect. 5.1.

The excess source noise ϵ_i was set to 0 for the majority (70%) of the stars, but for $i = 1$ through 30 it was set to $1000(31 - i)/30$ units, i.e., decreasing linearly from 1000 units to 0. Similarly, the excess attitude noise was set to 0 for 80% of the buckets, and to $1000(41 - j)/40$ units for buckets $j = 1$ through 40.

AGIS-like iterations between the source and attitude updates, including the simultaneous estimation of the excess noises, were performed for different fractions of outlier (using $f = 100$). In all cases, convergence was more or less reached in 4 simple iterations. This means that not only had the source and attitude parameters reached stable values at this point, but also the identification of outliers and the estimated excess noises were stable.

Figure 5 shows the development of the excess source noises ϵ_i in the four iterations for a case with 2% outliers. The red solid line shows the input (‘true’) values used to simulate the observations. It is seen that the true values are recovered, with only a slight ($\sim 5\%$) underestimation of the excess noise. Even with 20% outliers, the results after four iterations are quite good.

The corresponding development of the estimated excess attitude noises is shown in Fig. 6. In the case of 2% outliers, the excess noise is correctly estimated when the true noise is greater than about 100 units, but overestimated by some 30–50 units when the true noise is negligible. With 20% outliers, the excess noise is always overestimated by ~ 150 units or more.

FIGURE 5: The top four diagrams show the estimated excess source noises (ϵ_i ; blue circles) in the first four AGIS-like iterations, for a simulation with 2% outliers. The (red) solid line shows the excess noises assumed in the simulation, i.e., the ‘true’ values. The bottom-right diagram shows the result of the 4th iteration for a simulation with 20% outliers.

FIGURE 6: The top four diagrams show the estimated excess attitude noises (ϵ_{aj} ; blue circles) in the first four AGIS-like iterations, for a simulation with 2% outliers. The (red) solid line shows the excess noises assumed in the simulation, i.e., the ‘true’ values. The bottom-right diagram shows the result of the 4th iteration for a simulation with 20% outliers.

FIGURE 7: The top diagrams show the estimated number of outliers per source as function of the actual number of outliers. The bottom diagrams show the corresponding statistics per attitude buckets. The fraction of outliers is 2% in the left diagrams and 20% in the right diagrams.

Figure 7 shows the estimated number of outliers (i.e., with $w_\ell < 0.2$) versus the actual number of generated outliers (with $f = 100$). It is clear that some outliers are missed, and instead interpreted as excess attitude noise, but on the whole the outlier detection seems to work extremely well and in particular the results for the sources are very clean even in the presence of a quite excessive number of outliers.

6 Conclusions

A new way of representing the weights of the astrometric AL and AC observations is proposed. It consists of two excess noise contributions, one (ϵ_i) linked to each source (i), the other ($\epsilon_a(t)$) linked to the attitude and being a function of time and different in three axes ($a = \text{AL, ACP, ACF}$). Outliers are downweighted as before depending on the size of the residual compared with the *total* estimated noise. This prevents observations from being considered as outliers just because they occurred during a stretch of bad attitude data. In this scheme, the concept of ‘unit weight error’ is no longer used.

The algorithms for identifying outliers and estimating the excess noise levels are described in Sect. 3.1 and Appendix A for the sources, and in Sect. 3.2 for the attitude. Simplified numerical experiments reported in Sect. 5 demonstrate that the algorithms actually work even with a high percentage of outliers in the data.

The outlier identification and estimation of the excess noises need to be done iteratively between the source update and the attitude update, according to the ‘simple iteration’ scheme of AGIS. Judging from the present numerical experiments, a small number of iterations (~ 4) might be sufficient, but it seems likely that a bit more will be needed in the real situation. After these initial iterations, the weights and downweights can be fixed and the Conjugate Gradients algorithm applied.

The estimated excess source noise is obviously useful for selecting primary stars for AGIS. Similarly, the estimated excess attitude noise is relevant for micrometeoroid impact detection, either to set a reference noise level or for the actual detection (look for impacts in buckets with large noise). Obviously, both noise estimates are extremely valuable for monitoring mission health and adequacy of the attitude modelling.

The present algorithms (including a storage-efficient way of estimating quantiles) should be tested in AGISLab before being implemented in AGIS.

7 References

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Appendix A:

Source update algorithm including the estimation of the excess noise

In this Appendix we give a simple (and tested) algorithm to solve the following non-linear problem, equivalent to Eqs. (7)–(8). For brevity, the source index (i) is left out of the expressions below. The current estimate of the astrometric parameters can be thought of as a column vector, \mathbf{x} , of length $n = 5$. However, the actual values are irrelevant for the algorithm, which only produces an update δ to the astrometric parameters.

For a particular source, we are then given:

- the design matrix \mathbf{A} , of dimension $m \times n$, where m is the number of observations;
- the right-hand side \mathbf{h} , a column matrix of length m containing the raw residuals with respect to the current astrometric parameters \mathbf{x} ;
- the column matrix $\tilde{\sigma}$ of length m containing the current estimates of the photon plus attitude noise, $\tilde{\sigma}_\ell = [\sigma_\ell^2 + \epsilon_a^2(t_\ell)]^{1/2}$.

A certain downweighting function $w(z)$ is also given, together with a limiting value w_{lim} (e.g., = 0.2) below which an observation is counted as an outlier. We now ask for the following data:

- an update δ to the current estimate of the astrometric parameters (column vector of length n);
- the excess source noise $\epsilon \geq 0$ (a scalar);
- the downweighting factors \mathbf{w} (column matrix of length m);

such that

$$S(\delta, \epsilon^2) = \sum_{\ell} \frac{R_{\ell}^2(\delta)}{\tilde{\sigma}_{\ell}^2 + \epsilon^2} w\left(\frac{R_{\ell}(\delta)}{\sqrt{\tilde{\sigma}_{\ell}^2 + \epsilon^2}}\right) \quad (13)$$

is minimized, subject to the constraint

$$S_{\min}(\epsilon^2) \equiv \min_{\delta} S(\delta, \epsilon^2) \leq \nu \equiv m - m_{\text{out}} - n, \quad (14)$$

where m_{out} is the number of outliers, i.e., the cardinality of $\{\ell : w_{\ell} < e_{\text{lim}}\}$. The residuals $R_{\ell}(\delta)$ are the elements of the column vector $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{h} - \mathbf{A}\delta$. If $S_{\min}(0) \leq \nu$, then $\epsilon = 0$ and the corresponding δ are returned.

Auxiliary information provided by the solution includes the number of outliers m_{out} , the significance of the excess source noise D (equation 10), and the estimated covariance of the astrometric parameters \mathbf{V} .

The required procedure may be denoted

$$[\boldsymbol{\delta}, \mathbf{V}, \epsilon, D, \mathbf{w}] \leftarrow \mathcal{P}[\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{h}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}], \quad (15)$$

and at the end of this Appendix we give the pseudo-code for \mathcal{P} in terms of several simpler procedures $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \dots$, which we first define.

P1: Estimating the excess noise from given residuals

This problem is non-linear both because of the downweighting function $w(z)$ and because ϵ affects the relative weights of the observations, as well as which observations are downweighted. However, thanks to the redundancy of observations and the smoothness of $w(z)$, the solution $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ (and therefore \mathbf{R}) is not *strongly* dependent on ϵ . We can therefore consider the following simplified problem: given $\mathbf{R}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, and \mathbf{w} (and hence ν), find $y \equiv \epsilon^2 \geq 0$ such that

$$s(y) \equiv \sum_{\ell} R_{\ell}^2 w_{\ell} (\tilde{\sigma}_{\ell}^2 + y)^{-1} = \nu \quad (16)$$

if possible; otherwise $y = 0$.

To solve (16) we make use of the derivative

$$s'(y) = - \sum_{\ell} R_{\ell}^2 w_{\ell} (\tilde{\sigma}_{\ell}^2 + y)^{-2} \quad (17)$$

and note that $s'(y) < 0$ for all y , so $s(y)$ is strictly decreasing from its maximum $s(0)$ at $y = 0$. Therefore, the answer is $y = 0$ if $s(0) \leq \nu$.

If on the other hand $s(0) > \nu$, we need to solve the non-linear equation (16). This can be done by any standard iterative method, for example, the Newton–Raphson method. However, we have found the following variant to converge faster: at any point y , compute $s(y)$ and $s'(y)$; then an improved value is given by $y + \Delta y$, where

$$\Delta y = \frac{s(y)}{-s'(y)} \left(\frac{s(y)}{\nu} - 1 \right). \quad (18)$$

In practice at most 2 or 3 iterations are needed, starting from $y = 0$.³ The significance D of the excess noise is then computed according to (10). The above procedure is denoted

$$[\epsilon] \leftarrow \mathcal{P}_1[\mathbf{R}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}, \mathbf{w}, \nu]. \quad (19)$$

³Equation (18) is obtained by using a rational approximation $s(y) \simeq s_0/(s_1 + y)$ around the current y , rather than a linear approximation, as in the Newton–Raphson method. The coefficients s_0, s_1 are obtained by matching $s(y)$ and $s'(y)$ at the current point. The superiority of this approximation is due to its more reasonable behaviour for large y . Thus, already $s(0)$ and $s'(0)$ often give a fair first approximation $y_1 = -(s(0)/s'(0))(s(0)/\nu - 1)$, whereas the first Newton–Raphson step $y_1 = -(s(0) - \nu)/s'(0)$ grossly underestimates y if $s(0) \gg \nu$.

P2: Calculating the downweighting factors

Given a residual vector \mathbf{R} , the noise vector $\tilde{\sigma}_\ell$ and the excess source noise ϵ , the downweighting factors are calculated as

$$w_\ell = w \left(\frac{R_\ell}{\sqrt{\tilde{\sigma}_\ell^2 + \epsilon^2}} \right) \quad (20)$$

and m_{out} is obtained by counting the number of observations with $w_\ell < e_{\text{lim}}$. We denote this procedure

$$[\mathbf{w}, m_{\text{out}}] \leftarrow \mathcal{P}_2[\mathbf{R}, \tilde{\sigma}, \epsilon]. \quad (21)$$

P3: Initial robust dispersion estimate

The identification of outliers and the estimation of excess noises is a bootstrap procedure that needs to be initialized with some extremely robust estimate of the total dispersion of the residuals. For this we use (as in the old source update) half the intersextile range, ς . Thus, for a given residual vector \mathbf{R} we have the procedure

$$[\varsigma] \leftarrow \mathcal{P}_3[\mathbf{R}]. \quad (22)$$

P4: Calculating the update for fixed weights

A core part of the algorithm is the (non-iterative) calculation of the update vector for fixed weights, i.e., where the excess noise estimates are given, as well as the downweighting factors. This is in fact the procedure to be used as the source update in the Conjugate Gradient scheme, but it is also used in the inner iteration loop in order to determine the weights.

The source update is in this case obtained by a simple weighted least-squares procedure. In principle it could use either normal equations or (for improved numerical accuracy, at the expense of more arithmetic operations) orthogonal transformations. Here we use the normal equations. The update is thus obtained by forming and solving the normal equations

$$(\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{A}) \delta = \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{W}\mathbf{h}, \quad (23)$$

where \mathbf{W} is a diagonal $m \times m$ matrix with elements

$$W_\ell = w_\ell (\tilde{\sigma}_\ell^2 + \epsilon^2)^{-1} \quad (24)$$

along the diagonal. The residual vector is

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{h} - \mathbf{A}\delta. \quad (25)$$

This procedure is formally denoted

$$[\delta, \mathbf{R}] \leftarrow \mathcal{P}_4[\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{h}, \tilde{\sigma}, \mathbf{w}, \epsilon]. \quad (26)$$

Appendix B:

Storage-efficient sequential estimation of quantiles

Equation (11) uses the 68% quantile of the set of values $\{x_\ell\}$ accumulated in bucket j . Quantiles are usually calculated by storing the individual values, sorting them, and performing an inverse interpolation of their rank. Indeed, it can be shown that the *exact* calculation of a quantile (such as the median) of N values in a single pass through the data requires storage that scales linearly with N . This means that at least one number per observation must be preserved, or a total of some 10^{11} numbers for 10^8 primary stars. Although this is not impossible, it is clearly very inconvenient, and it is desirable to find a more efficient way.

It is then necessary to resort to an approximate calculation, which should be acceptable for the present application. A large number of algorithms for storage-efficient estimation of quantiles are described in the literature; see for example Greenwald & Khanna (2001), Gilbert et al. (2002) and references therein. Typically these algorithms require storage that scales as $\log N$ or $\log^2 N$. Some require prior knowledge of N , which makes them less useful for our purpose, and some are unnecessarily complex, as they for example allow values to be removed from the set as well as added. A reasonably simple and efficient algorithm that might fit our purpose is given by Greenwald & Khanna (2001). However, it still requires storage of at least a few hundred numbers per bucket. Thus, if we contemplate a bucket size of 100 s ($\sim 5 \times 10^6$ buckets for 5 yr), the storage requirement is still quite significant ($\sim 10^9$ numbers).

Feldman & Shavitt (Feldman & Shavitt, 2007) give an extremely simple algorithm (called FAME) for sequential estimation of the *median* (i.e., the 50% quantile), which only requires the storage of two (!) numbers per bucket. It is probably much less accurate than the more sophisticated algorithms, and it may fail if the data do not arrive in reasonably ‘random’ fashion. But its simplicity is appealing, and perhaps it can be modified to estimate the 68% quantile instead of the median.

However, for the present application a simpler solution could be to accumulate a histogram of $\log x_\ell$, from which any quantile can then be estimated by inverse interpolation. For example, a bin size of 0.1 neper would allow to estimate any quantile to within the nearest bin, i.e., with a maximum relative error of $\pm 5\%$, which may be fully adequate. The required number of histogram bins is then about 23 per decade in ϵ_a . For example, if residuals from 10 μas to 100 mas need to be considered (4 decades), then the histograms could be stored in less than 100 short integers per bucket, which is significantly less than for the Greenwald & Khanna (2001) algorithm with similar precision.